

Conductance and ion association studies of diammine-bis-1-amidino-*o*-methylureacobalt(III) monochloride in methanol + water mixtures at different temperatures

Gopal Chandra Bag, N. Mohondas Singh and N. Rajmuhon Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Manipur University, Canchipur, Imphal-795 003, India

Fax : 91-0385-221429

Manuscript received 29 February 2000, revised 15 January 2001, accepted 16 January 2001

Conductance of diammine-bis-1-amidino-*o*-methylureacobalt(III) monochloride has been measured in water and varying water + methanol (W-M) mixtures at 5–40°. The limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) and the ion-association constant (K_A) for the complex salt in these mixtures have been evaluated using Shedlovsky equation. Based on the composition dependence of the Walden product, the influence of the mixed solvent composition on the solvation of ions has been discussed. Temperature variation of the association constant has also been studied to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters. The results have been discussed in terms of ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions.

Transport properties are very useful for the study of ionic solvation. These properties can give information on the effective size of a moving particle in solution. These properties are sensitive to strong ion-solvent interactions, which increase the effective size of the ions, and also to any modification in the structure of the solvents¹. In general, properties such as conductance can be measured very precisely at low concentrations and reliable values of infinite dilution are readily obtained. It is hoped that a systematic coverage of properties of typical ions and solvents or mixed solvents will give an overall view of the main aspects of solvation. Information on ion-solvent interactions can be obtained both from Λ_0 and K_A derived from the concentration dependence of Λ .

In continuation of our conductometric studies on octahedral Co^{III} complexes in water and water + methanol², the present work aims at determining the conductance values of the solution of diammine-bis-1-amidino-*o*-methylureacobalt(III) monochloride in water + methanol ($X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.0000, 0.0588, 0.1233, 0.1942, 0.2727, 0.3600, 0.4576, 0.6923, 0.8351$ and 1.0000) mixtures at 5–40° to examine the validity of Shedlovsky conductance equation. The association constants and Walden products for the Co^{III} complex have been evaluated. These values have been used to discuss qualitatively the nature of the ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions of the octahedral Co^{III} complex in W-M mixtures. Temperature variation of K_A has been studied to get the thermodynamic parameters as a function of the solvent composition.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data of conductance measurements of 1 : 1 Co^{III} complex in W-M mixtures after solvent correction were analyzed using Shedlovsky extrapolation techni-

que³. Shedlovsky method involves the linear extrapolation using eq. (1),

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda S(z)} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \left(\frac{K_A}{\Lambda_0^2} \right) (C \Lambda_{\pm}^2 S(z)) \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the equivalent conductance at a concentration C (mol dm⁻³), Λ_0 the limiting equivalent conductance and K_A the observed association constant. The other symbols are given by

$$S(z) = \left(\frac{z}{2} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{z}{2} \right)^2} \right)^2, \quad z = \left[\frac{(\alpha \Lambda_0 + \beta)}{\Lambda_0^{3/2}} \right] (C \Lambda)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{0.8204 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}}, \quad \beta = \frac{82.501}{\eta(DT)^{1/2}}$$

where D is the dielectric constant, and η the viscosity of the medium. The degree of dissociation (τ) is related to $S(z)$ by

$$\tau = \frac{\Lambda S(z)}{\Lambda_0}$$

f_{\pm} , the mean activity coefficient of the free ions, was calculated using eq. (2),

$$-\log f_{\pm} = \frac{A(\tau C)^{1/2}}{1 + BR'(\tau C)^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } A = \frac{1.8246 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}} \quad B = \frac{0.5029 \times 10^{10}}{(DT)^{1/2}}$$

R' is the maximum centre to centre distance between the ions in the solvent separated ion-pair. There exists at present no precise method⁴ for determining the value of R' . In order to treat the data in our system, the R' value is assumed to be $R' = a + d$, where a , the sum of crystallographic radii of the ions, is approximately equal to 5 Å and d is the average distance corresponding to the side of a

cell occupied by a solvent molecule. The distance $d(\text{\AA})$ is given by⁵

$$d = 1.183 (M/\rho)^{1/3}$$

where M is the molecular weight of the solvent and ρ the density of the solution.

$$M_{\text{avg}} = \frac{M_1 M_2}{X_1 M_2 + X_2 M_1}$$

where X_1 is the mole fraction of methanol of molecular weight M_1 and X_2 that of water of molecular weight M_2 . The values of Λ_0 and K_A are calculated using eq. (1) by an iterative procedure, the details of which is mentioned elsewhere². All calculations were carried out on IBM PC-AT. The results of Λ_0 , K_A and $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ at different temperatures are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The values of limiting equivalent conductances Λ_0 (S cm²), association constant K_A (dm³ mol⁻¹), Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) obtained by Shedlovsky technique for the Co^{III} complex in water + methanol mixtures at different temperatures

X_{methanol}	Temp. = 5°		Temp. = 10°		Temp. = 15°		Temp. = 20°		Temp. = 25°		Temp. = 30°		Temp. = 35°		Temp. = 40°			
	Λ_0	K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	Λ_0	K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	Λ_0	K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	Λ_0	K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	Λ_0	K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	Λ_0	K_A	
0.0000	100.65	1538.29	152.99	113.36	1220.22	147.71												
0.0588	88.51	1672.60	158.25	96.13	1303.39	155.44												
0.1233	75.28	1700.59	162.91	83.70	1389.02	164.30												
0.1942	69.68	1763.34	167.30	76.94	1463.26	167.73												
0.2727	65.04	1849.18	170.53	72.68	1608.82	170.07												
0.3600	60.51	1989.00	176.02	69.33	1702.27	172.70												
0.4576	73.05	2192.17	170.28	79.06	1812.09	169.19												
0.6923	87.80	2440.11	144.43	95.54	2153.84	141.02												
0.8351	109.97	2671.04	127.23	114.12	2322.97	120.95												
1.0000	135.79	2821.93	99.64	140.04	2502.55	96.07												
0.0000	121.12	996.06	143.02	130.66	657.15	130.26												
0.0588	105.64	1026.48	152.76	111.99	709.06	140.32												
0.1233	86.02	1150.87	151.57	98.36	840.52	149.11												
0.1942	83.20	1220.55	165.03	89.55	935.34	150.44												
0.2727	80.17	1353.04	166.39	87.25	1060.64	154.43												
0.3600	80.55	1485.10	166.98	86.30	1192.18	155.16												
0.4576	84.21	1600.23	166.07	89.70	1302.86	150.79												
0.6923	98.45	1941.64	128.67	103.88	1643.27	123.82												
0.8351	116.96	2163.80	111.94	122.25	1843.52	106.63												
1.0000	143.43	2339.06	91.51	145.21	2083.52	85.82												
0.0000	138.66	344.78	122.96	148.48	308.40	118.57												
0.0588	122.64	484.33	134.66	126.77	371.59	124.49												
0.1233	105.48	538.64	138.81	112.81	458.07	129.17												
0.1942	96.30	629.81	139.06	104.54	569.47	131.41												
0.2727	95.14	777.01	142.90	103.58	673.72	137.66												
0.3600	92.14	894.10	144.62	102.35	819.39	139.03												
0.4576	97.02	1035.04	141.75	104.59	936.52	132.72												
0.6923	108.22	1406.91	116.98	109.02	1302.37	105.10												
0.8351	125.14	1606.76	100.74	127.00	1513.27	92.20												
1.0000	148.89	1866.95	82.34	151.19	1733.21	77.86												
0.0000	155.15	161.36	111.171	164.88	95.73	107.31												
0.0588	137.25	260.73	119.88	142.09	166.05	112.68												
0.1233	120.15	365.00	121.08	128.06	263.30	115.51												
0.1942	110.70	449.37	122.99	118.32	317.16	117.02												
0.2727	108.81	556.47	125.89	117.10	441.15	117.45												
0.3600	106.18	688.10	127.20	114.32	592.47	119.46												
0.4576	107.18	840.62	123.69	115.48	746.09	115.13												
0.6923	116.00	1199.28	101.15	120.28	1071.46	94.30												
0.8351	130.44	1387.07	87.79	134.05	1294.92	83.11												
1.0000	154.72	1658.29	74.73	156.81	1515.95	70.72												

The variation of Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) with X_1 at 10, 20, 30 and 40° are shown in Fig. 1. The values of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ increase with increase in X_1 upto about 0.36 and thereafter it

Fig. 1. Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) and viscosity (η) as a function of X_1 , the mole fraction of methanol in methanol + water mixture : (O) 10°, (□) 20°, (Δ) 30° and (●) 40°, η at (■) 25°.

increases rapidly. The viscosity of W-M mixtures also passes through a maximum at about $X_1 = 0.36$. It is interesting to note that the Λ_0 values of the solute decrease upto this mole fraction of methanol and then increase in methanol-rich region at all temperatures from 5 to 40°, indicating maximum methanol-water interaction in the region $X_1 = 0.36$.

The variation of the Walden product reflects the change of total solvation⁶. The value of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ would be constant only if the effective radius of the ions were the same in different media. Since most ions are solvated in solution the constancy of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ is not expected. The increase of the product indicates the weak solvation of ions which attains a maximum value at $X_1 = 0.36$. The decrease of the product indicates an increase of the hydrophobic solvation with increasing concentration of methanol. The variation of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ with X_1 is due to an electrochemical equilibrium between the cations with the solvent molecules on one hand and the selective solvation of ions on the other with the change in composition of the mixed solvents and the temperature of the solution.

On the water-rich side there exists a region, where water structure remains more or less intact as methanol molecules are added interstitially into cavities in the structure. As more and more methanol is added the cavities are progressively filled, water-methanol interactions become stronger and in turn producing maximum Walden product. Further addition of methanol results in progressive disruption of water structure and the ions become solvated with the other component of the solvent mixture (*viz.* methanol). The effect would be more in case of a solution at a higher temperature. As expected, Λ_0 values increase with rise in temperature linearly irrespective of the nature of the solvent.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters ΔG° (kJ mol⁻¹), ΔH° (kJ mol⁻¹), ΔS° (kJ K⁻¹ mol⁻¹), E_s (kJ mol⁻¹) and A of the Co^{III} complex in water + methanol mixtures using Shedlovsky method at different temperatures

	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°
				(X ₁ = 0.0000)				
ΔG°	-16.97	-16.72	-16.53	-15.81	-14.48	-14.44	-13.02	-11.87
ΔH°			-57.84					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-146.94	-145.22	-143.36	-143.37	-145.43	-143.16	-145.45	-146.80
E_s			9.37					
$10^{-3} A$			6.04					
				(X ₁ = 0.0588)				
ΔG°	-17.16	-16.88	-16.60	-15.99	-15.32	-14.91	-14.25	-13.30
ΔH°			-47.52					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-109.15	-108.21	-107.31	-107.55	-107.99	-107.57	-107.97	-109.28
E_s			10.27					
$10^{-3} A$			6.52					
				(X ₁ = 0.1233)				
ΔG°	-17.20	-17.03	-16.88	-16.41	-15.58	-15.44	-15.11	-14.50
ΔH°			-39.55					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-80.35	-79.53	-78.67	-78.94	-80.39	-79.53	-79.31	-79.99
E_s			11.01					
$10^{-3} A$			8.86					
				(X ₁ = 0.1942)				
ΔG°	-17.28	-17.15	-17.02	-16.67	-15.97	-15.98	-15.65	-14.99
ΔH°			-35.43					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-65.25	-64.56	-63.89	-63.99	-65.27	-64.16	-64.19	-65.27
E_s			11.05					
$10^{-3} A$			8.31					
				(X ₁ = 0.2727)				
ΔG°	-17.39	-17.38	-17.27	-16.98	-16.49	-16.41	-16.19	-15.85
ΔH°			-30.56					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-47.35	-46.55	-46.12	-46.32	-47.19	-46.68	-46.63	-46.97
E_s			11.82					
$10^{-3} A$			11.10					
				(X ₁ = 0.3600)				
ΔG°	-17.56	-17.51	-17.49	-17.26	-16.84	-16.90	-16.74	-16.62
ΔH°			-26.75					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-33.04	-32.63	-32.14	-32.37	-33.24	-32.49	-32.48	-32.35
E_s			12.05					
$10^{-3} A$			11.91					
				(X ₁ = 0.4576)				
ΔG°	-17.78	-17.65	-17.67	-17.48	-17.20	-17.24	-17.28	-17.22
ΔH°			-22.55					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	-17.15	-79.31	-16.94	-17.29	-17.94	-17.52	-17.20	-17.02
E_s			9.45					
$10^{-3} A$			4.36					
				(X ₁ = 0.6923)				
ΔG°	-18.03	-18.06	-18.13	-18.04	-17.96	-18.07	-18.16	-18.16
ΔH°			-17.34					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	2.48	2.54	2.74	2.39	-2.08	2.41	2.66	2.62
E_s			6.07					
$10^{-3} A$			1.24					
				(X ₁ = 0.8351)				
ΔG°	-18.19	-18.24	-18.39	-18.32	-18.29	-18.45	-18.53	-18.65
ΔH°			-14.99					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	11.50	11.48	11.80	11.36	11.07	11.41	11.49	11.69
E_s			4.09					
$10^{-3} A$			0.65					
				(X ₁ = 1.0000)				
ΔG°	-18.37	-18.41	-18.58	-18.62	-18.66	-18.79	-18.99	-19.06
ΔH°			-12.49					
$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	21.14	20.91	21.13	20.91	20.69	20.78		20.98
E_s			2.91					
$10^{-3} A$			0.48					

The experimentally determined K_A s are found to increase with increase in X_1 (linear plots) which indicates an increased association as methanol is added to water. Large

values of K_A and exothermic ion-pair formation indicate the presence of specific short range interaction between the ions.

Since the conductance of an ion depends on its mobility, it is reasonable to treat the conductance data similar to the one that employs, for rate processes taking place with change of temperature⁸, i.e.

$$\Lambda_0 = A e^{-E_s/RT}$$

$$\text{or } \ln \Lambda_0 = \ln A - E_s/RT$$

where A is the frequency factor, R the ideal gas constant and E_s the Arrhenius activation energy of transport processes. Thus from the plot of $\log \Lambda_0$ vs $1/T$ for the octahedral Co^{III} complex in all the solvents, the E_s values have been computed from the slope⁹ and are recorded in Table 2. A perusal of Table 2 shows that the values of E_s increase with increase in X_1 upto $X_1 = 0.36$, and thereafter decreases rapidly. It follows that in water-rich region upto $X_1 = 0.36$, the Co^{III} complex ion require higher activation energy for the transport processes as the methanol content in the mixed solvent increases but reverse is the case beyond $X_1 = 0.36$. Since a reaction which requires higher activation energy is slow at ordinary temperatures, it indicates lower mobilities of the ions in the solutions and hence lower Λ_0 values. Beyond $X_1 = 0.36$ as the activation energy decreases the Λ_0 values increases with X_1 .

The free energy change (ΔG°) for association is calculated from the relation¹⁰, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_A$. The heat of association (ΔH°) is obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log K_A$ vs $1/T$. The ΔH° values obtained are found to increase systematically with the composition of the mixed solvent. The entropy change (ΔS°) is calculated from the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation, $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$. The values of these thermodynamic functions are given in Table 2. The negative values of ΔH° indicates that ion association processes are exothermic in nature in all solvents at all temperatures. At a particular temperature ΔG° becomes more negative with the increase in X_1 . This indicates that ion-pair association is favoured with lowering of dielectric constant of the medium. A positive entropy change is explained on the assumption that the iceberg structure around the cation is broken when association takes place leading to an increase in the degree of disorderliness¹¹.

Conclusion : K_A s increases with the increase in X_1 , Λ_0 values increase linearly with the increase in temperature. Ion association process is exothermic in nature. Ion solvation is minimum in the mixture whose viscosity is maximum. In methanol-rich region ion association processes are less energy-consuming and more stabilised than in water-rich region.

Experimental

The octahedral Co^{III} complex, diammine-bis-1-amidino-*o*-methylureacobalt(III) monochloride was prepared according to the reported procedure¹². The purity of the sample was determined by conventional chemical analyses and spectral measurements. The values were in good agreement

with the literature values. Methanol (Qualigens) was treated by the standard procedure¹³. For preparing aqueous solution of methanol $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.0588, 0.1233, 0.1942, 0.2727, 0.3600, 0.4576, 0.6923$ and 0.8351 , water of specific conductance of the order $< 2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ was used. All the solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed samples of the electrolyte in solvent mixtures (w/w). All the viscosity, dielectric constant and density values were interpolated from literature values¹⁴. A Systronics 306 conductivity bridge (accuracy $\pm 0.1\%$) with a dip type immersion conductivity cell was used. The details of experimental procedure has been described earlier¹⁵.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (G.C.B.) thanks U.G.C., Guwahati, for a Teacher Fellowship. The authors are also thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Manipur University, for facilities.

References

1. B. E. Conway, J. O'M. Bockris and E. Yeager, "Comprehensive Treatise of Electrochemistry", Plenum Press, New York, 1983, Vol. 5.
2. G. C. Bag, N. M. Singh and N. R. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 146.
3. T. Shedlovsky and R. L. Kay, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 151.
4. B. Per, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1977, **31**, 869.
5. R. M. Fuoss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 2427.
6. U. G. K. Raju, B. Sethuram and T. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 293.
7. S. Glasstone, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", East-West Press, New Delhi, 1942.
8. U. N. Dash and N. N. Pasupalak, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 88.
9. F. Corradini, A. Marchetti, M. Tgagliazucchi, L. Tassi L and G. Tossi, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1993, **89**, 1359.
10. J. F. Coetzee and C. D. Ritchie, "Solute-Solvent Interactions", Marcel-Dekker, New York, 1976, Vol. 2.
11. M. K. De and R. L. Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 67.
12. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 121.
13. A. Wiesberger, "Techniques in Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1955, Vol. 7.
14. C. D. Hodgman, R. C. Weast and S. M. Selby, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., Cleveland, 1956-57, p. 2257; Y. Y. Akhadov, "Dielectric Properties of Binary Solutions - A Data Handbook", Pergamon, Oxford, 1981, p. 274; J. Timmermanns, "The Physicochemical Constants of Binary Systems in Concentrated Solutions", Interscience, New York, Vol. 4, p. 786.
15. G. C. Bag, N. R. Singh and N. R. Singh, *Chem. Environ. Res.*, 1998, **7**, 221.